

Nonlinear Deformation Analysis of Geocell-Reinforced Foundations with Granular Shear Layers

Sidi Mohammed DAOUD¹, Nouredine ELMEICHE¹, Ismail MECHAB², Habib TROUZINE¹³, Mourad MEGHACHOU¹

¹Civil and Environmental Engineering Laboratory (LGCE), Faculty of Technology, Djilali Liabes University, Sidi Bel Abbes 22000, Algeria

²Department of Mechanical Engineering, Laboratory Mechanics Physics of Materials (LMPM), University of Sidi Bel Abbes, Sidi Bel Abbes 22000, Algeria

³ Civil Engineering Department, Tlemcen University, Tlemcen 13000, Algeria

Corresponding author: Sidi Mohammed DAOUD

E-mail: sidimohamed.daoud@univ-sba.dz / daoudmed22@yahoo.fr

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Abstract

This study developed an analytical model to simulate the behavior of a geocell-reinforced soil layer resting on a granular bed overlying soft soil. The model uses both linear and nonlinear formulations of the Winkler and Pasternak models to analyze the effects of various parameters on the response of the geocell. The geocell is modeled as a finite-length beam with flexural rigidity, and the underlying soil is represented by Winkler springs connected to a Pasternak shear layer. The results show that the nonlinearity of the models significantly influences the displacements, particularly in the vicinity of the loaded zones. Including the Pasternak model considerably reduces the displacements, with a reduction of 75% for large loads. In addition, parametric studies show that increasing the shear modulus and the granular layer's thickness improves the system's response. At the same time, the effect of the flexural rigidity of the geocell becomes negligible above a certain threshold. These results highlight the importance of considering the nonlinear behavior of the soil and mechanical interactions to optimize the performance of reinforced cellular layers.

Keywords: Geocell reinforcement, Winkler and Pasternak models, Flexural rigidity, Nonlinear behaviour, Shear modulus

1 Introduction

The need for good-quality land is constantly increasing due to the rapid development of construction in various sectors, such as civil and industrial buildings, road and rail infrastructure, bridges, and many others. Various soil improvement techniques are used to meet these requirements.

Among these techniques, soil reinforcement with geosynthetics has found wide application, with benefits such as reduced settlement, increased bearing capacity, and significant savings in the use of embankments (Leitão Borges & Silva Cardoso, 2001), (Sitharam & Sireesh, 2006), (Arulrajah et al., 2009), (El-Shesheny et al., 2014), (Wu et al., 2017)

Geocells, a type of geosynthetic with a three-dimensional honeycomb structure, are made of polymer. The confinement of the infill soil by the cell walls, as well as their interconnection, allows the geocell mat to act as a rigid layer, increasing its bearing capacity and evenly

distributing the loads applied to the underlying soil (Rajagopal et al., 1999),(Dash et al., 2001), (Koerner, 2012). In recent years, geocells have been widely used to construct low-maintenance roads in difficult soil conditions (Banerjee et al., 2023).

Several experimental and numerical studies have been carried out to assess the effectiveness of geocells in soil reinforcement. For example,(Dash et al., 2019) showed that a geocell-reinforced layer reduces contact pressures and deformations of the underlying soil with increasing layer width. (Hegde & Sitharam, 2013) They found that cellular reinforcement of sand and clay soils improved the bearing capacity by 2.4 to 3.2 times compared to unreinforced soils.

In addition to experimental studies, several studies have used mathematical models to analyze Geocell-reinforced soils in paving and foundation applications.

The modeling of geocells as flexural rigid beams has been used to analyze the behavior of reinforced soils. (Qu, 2009) proposed a model where the geocell mat is represented as a beam resting on an elastic foundation, with an equivalent modulus of elasticity considering the geocells' tensile and compressive strength to determine the deformation under uniform loading. (Zhang et al., 2018) developed a simplified model for a geocell-reinforced granular layer embankment over soft soil with stone columns; the cushion was modeled as an Euler-Bernoulli beam, and the columns as elastoplastic springs. In a study (Bhatra & Maheshwari, 2019), rails on a geocell-reinforced soft clay embankment were modeled using infinite Euler-Bernoulli beams with a granular sublayer represented by a Pasternak shear layer. The results showed the influence of Burger model parameters and load rate on the rail response.

Other mathematical models have used the modeling of the geocell by a Pasternak shear layer; we cite the work of (Aboobacker et al., 2015), who developed a mathematical formulation to study the behavior of a rigid foundation resting on a granular layer reinforced by geocells over soft soil. In this model, the reinforced layer is modeled as a Pasternak shear layer, while the soft soil is represented by a series of Winkler springs. The study distinguishes between linear (small settlements) and nonlinear (large settlements) responses. The results show that the shear stiffness of the reinforced granular bed plays a significant role in improving the bearing capacity. The influence of the width of the shear layer, the shear stiffness, and the ultimate bearing capacity of the soft soil were also investigated.

(Sireesh & Madhav, 2011) also presented a theoretical formulation for a geocell-reinforced soft soil supporting a rigid footing. In this model, the geocell is modeled as a Pasternak shear layer with variable width and height parameters. The study showed that adjusting the stiffness of the soft soil and geocell layers improves the bearing capacity of the reinforced soil.

This study proposes an analytical model to simulate the behavior of a cellular layer resting on foundation soil. By integrating the Winkler and Pasternak models in their linear and nonlinear formulations, the effects of different parameters on the response of the reinforced system can be analyzed. The geocell is modeled as a finite-length beam whose flexural rigidity is considered in the calculations. The underlying soil is represented by nonlinear springs according to the Winkler model, connected by a Pasternak shear layer. The main objective is to study the influence of the soil behavior's nonlinearity, the geocell's flexural rigidity, the granular layer's shear modulus, and the thickness of this layer on the displacements obtained.

2 Analytical model

This study aims to develop an analytical model to simulate the behavior of a geocell-reinforced soil layer, considering the Winkler and Pasternak models and the nonlinearity of the soil beneath the geocell layer.

The geocell layer is considered a finite beam subjected to the geocells' weight and the overlying soil's weight, as shown in **Figure 1**. Although geocells are inherently flexible, they behave as a composite material with significant flexural rigidity when the overlying soil is compacted. This behavior has been confirmed in several studies of reinforced soils. (Dey & Basudhar, 2008, 2006; Fakher & Jones, 2001; Maheshwari et al., 2004, 2006; Maheshwari & Babu, 2017; Mamatha et al., 2019; Tang & Yang, 2013).

The response of the soil under the geocell is modeled using Pasternak's two-parameter model with a nonlinear formulation that considers the soil's elastoplastic behavior and its shear strength (Kerr, 1964; Pasternak, 1954). The geocell layer is represented as a beam with flexural rigidity EI , length $2L$, width b , and height h . The underlying soil is assumed to rest on a nonlinear elastic foundation, with a granular layer (shear layer) of thickness h_s interposed under the geocell.

The beam is subjected to a distributed linear load p , representing the weight of the fill, and a concentrated load F applied at its center.

Due to the model's symmetry, only the right half of the beam ($x \geq 0$) is studied. Considering the boundary conditions, the differential equations governing the system are deduced from the equilibrium of a differential element of the geocell.

Figure 1 Geocell model on a Pasternak foundation.

The nonlinear response in terms of the load-settlement relationship can be represented by the hyperbolic relationship proposed by (Kondner, 1963) for the Winkler model and, similarly, for the shear layer (C. Ghosh & Madhav, 1994). The following expression delineates the relationship above:

$$q = \frac{k_s w}{1 + \frac{k_s}{q_u} w} - \frac{G h_s}{\left(1 + \frac{G}{\tau_u} \frac{dw}{dx}\right)^2} \frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} \quad (1)$$

In this equation, k_s is the vertical soil reaction modulus, representing the spring stiffness of the Winkler model; q_u is the ultimate bearing capacity of the soil foundation; G and τ_u are the ultimate shear modulus and shear strength of the granular fill layer, respectively; and w represents the vertical settlement.

The equilibrium of forces and moments is analyzed for a uniaxial element, as illustrated in **Figure 2**; the element under consideration is subjected at its extremities to the moment M , the shear force V , and the tensile force T . A uniformly distributed surcharge p is applied to its upper surface, and the underlying soil exerts a reaction q on its lower surface.

If the element's weight is taken into account, the equilibrium equation for the moments is expressed as follows:

$$M + dM - M - Vdx - qbdx \frac{dx}{2} - bpdx \frac{dx}{2} = 0 \quad (2)$$

Figure 2 Forces acting on a geocell element

By neglecting the last two terms:

$$\frac{dM}{dx} - V = 0 \quad (3)$$

The equilibrium of vertical forces enables the following equation to be derived:

$$-V + (V + dV) - bqdx + bpdx = 0 \quad (4)$$

Combining equations (1) and (4) gives:

$$\frac{dV}{dx} = \frac{bk_s w}{1 + \frac{k_s w}{q_u}} - \frac{bGh_s}{\left(1 + \frac{G}{\tau_u} \frac{dw}{dx}\right)^2} \frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} - bp \quad (5)$$

By deriving equation (3) with respect to x and using the relationship between bending moment M and curvature, given by $M = -EI d^2 w / dx^2$, equations (5) can be written as follows :

$$EI \frac{d^4 w}{dx^4} + \frac{bk_s w}{1 + \frac{k_s w}{q_u}} - \frac{bGh_s}{\left(1 + \frac{G}{\tau_u} \frac{dw}{dx}\right)^2} \frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} = bp \quad (6)$$

By normalizing the terms according to:

$$W = \frac{w}{L} \text{ and } \xi = \frac{x}{L}$$

Thus equation (6) becomes:

$$\frac{EI}{L^3} \frac{d^4 W}{d\xi^4} + \frac{bLk_s W}{1 + \frac{Lk_s W}{q_u}} - \frac{bGh_s}{L \left(1 + \frac{G}{\tau_u} \frac{dW}{d\xi}\right)^2} \frac{d^2 W}{d\xi^2} = bp \quad (7)$$

Multiplying equation (7) by $\frac{L^3}{EI}$, gives:

$$\frac{d^4W}{d\xi^4} + \frac{bL^4k_sW}{EI\left(1 + \frac{Lk_s}{q_u}W\right)} - \frac{L^2bGh_s}{EI\left(1 + \frac{G}{\tau_u}\frac{dW}{d\xi}\right)^2} \frac{d^2W}{d\xi^2} = \frac{L^3bp}{EI} \quad (8)$$

The differential equation (8) can be expressed as a function of the following dimensionless parameters:

$$k_s^* = \frac{k_sbL^4}{EI}, G^* = \frac{Gh_sL^2b}{EI}, \alpha = \frac{k_sL}{q_u}, \beta = \frac{G}{\tau_u}, p^* = \frac{p}{Lk_s}, F^* = \frac{F}{k_sbL^2}$$

This gives the following equation:

$$\frac{d^4W}{d\xi^4} + \frac{k_s^*W}{(1 + \alpha W)} - \frac{G^*}{\left(1 + \beta \frac{dW}{d\xi}\right)^2} \frac{d^2W}{d\xi^2} = k_s^*p^* \quad (9)$$

In the following section, equation (9) will be solved using the finite difference method, and the half-length of the geocell L will be discretized into 100 points for a more detailed analysis.

This gives:

$$\begin{aligned} W_{i+2} - \left(4 + \frac{G^*\Delta\xi^2}{\left(1 + \frac{1}{2}\frac{\beta(W_{i+1} - W_{i-1})}{\Delta\xi}\right)^2} \right) W_{i+1} \\ + \left(6 + \frac{2G^*\Delta\xi^2}{\left(1 + \frac{1}{2}\frac{\beta(W_{i+1} - W_{i-1})}{\Delta\xi}\right)^2} + \frac{k_s^*\Delta\xi^4}{(1 + \alpha W_i)} \right) W_i \\ - \left(4 + \frac{G^*\Delta\xi^2}{\left(1 + \frac{1}{2}\frac{\beta(W_{i+1} - W_{i-1})}{\Delta\xi}\right)^2} \right) W_{i-1} + W_{i-2} = \Delta\xi^4 k_s^* p^* \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

The boundary conditions in terms of non-dimensional parameters are as follows:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{dW}{d\xi} \Big|_{\xi=0} = 0 \\ -EI \frac{d^3W}{d\xi^3} \Big|_{\xi=0} = \frac{F^*}{2} \\ \frac{d^2W}{d\xi^2} \Big|_{\xi=1} = 0 \\ \frac{d^3W}{d\xi^3} \Big|_{\xi=1} = 0 \end{array} \right. \quad (11)$$

Using the Newton-Raphson method, the solution was obtained for a convergence criterion of:

$$\left| \frac{W_i^k - W_i^{k-1}}{W_i^k} \right| < 10^{-7}$$

3 Validation

To validate the present study, the solution proposed by (Zhang et al., 2009) was compared without taking into account the interface friction. Equation (9) was simplified. This simplification neglects the nonlinearity terms of the Winkler model by assuming $\alpha = 0$ and omitting the Pasternak term.

$$\frac{d^4W}{d\xi^4} + k_s^*W = k_s^*p^* \quad (12)$$

In this analysis, the data obtained from the (Zhang et al., 2009) solution is used as a reference to validate the proposed model. The used values are:

$b = 500\text{mm}$; $h = 150\text{mm}$; $L = 3000\text{mm}$; $E = 50 \times 10^6 \text{ Pa}$; $k_s = 5 \times 10^6 \text{ N/m}$.

Figure 3 compares the curves for displacement as a function of force F to assess the accuracy of the analytical model. The results show good agreement between the solution of (Zhang et al., 2009) and the solution obtained in the present study.

Figure 3 Comparison of F-w curve with those of (Zhang et al., 2009)

4 Parametric study

It is well established that soils exhibit nonlinear behavior in their constitutive relationships (C. Ghosh & Madhav, 1994; Maheshwari & Babu, 2017; Saha Roy & Deb, 2022; Sireesh et al., 2016). Incorporating these nonlinear relationships into analyses can lead to significantly different responses than those obtained with linear models.

Table 1 provides hypothetical values for the various terms of the parametric study to assess the influence of nonlinearity and the various parameters on the displacements. These include the applied force F , the shear modulus G , and the flexural rigidity EI of the geocell.

Table 1 input parameters

Parameter	Symbol	Range of values	Unit
Half-length of the geocell	L	3	m
Width of the geocell	b	50	cm
Height of the geocell	h	15	cm
Height of shear layer	h_s	5 - 50	cm

Flexural rigidity	EI	0.7 - 14	kN.m ²
Self-Weight per Unit volume of soil	γ_s	18	kN/m ³
Modulus of subgrade reaction of soil (Bowles, 1968)	k_s	5	MN/m ³
Shear modulus of granular layer (Kramer & Stewart, 2024)	G	1 - 5	kPa
Ultimate bearing capacity of soil (Bowles, 1968)	q_u	300	kPa
Ultimate shear strength (Bell, 2013)	τ_u	100	kPa
Uniform line load	p	80	kN/m
Point load	F	1 - 100	kN

4.1 Influence of the nonlinearity of the Winkler model

It is essential to consider the soil's nonlinear behavior to obtain more accurate and reliable results (B. Ghosh et al., 2017). To evaluate the influence of the nonlinear Winkler model on the geocell displacement and exclude the Pasternak model, the following parameters were selected: $EI = 7\text{kN.m}^2$, $k_s = 5\text{ MN/m}^3$, $q_u = 300\text{ kPa}$, $F = 100\text{kN}$.

Figure 4 Comparison of displacement profiles for linear and nonlinear Winkler models of foundation soils

As illustrated in **Figure 4**, a comparison has been made between the deformation profiles obtained for the linear and nonlinear formulations of the Winkler model. Additionally, the non-dimensional displacement of the cellular layer has been calculated using the parameters defined above. The maximum displacement is observed at the center of the layer, with a difference of 80% between the displacements of the linear and nonlinear profiles, which decreases progressively to reach 38% at the end of the geocell. As displacement increases, the impact of nonlinearity becomes more pronounced, correlating with rising stress levels. The soil exhibits nonlinear behavior in the vicinity of the load zone, where stresses are elevated. Consequently, the geocell reinforcement's response is substantially influenced by nonlinearity up to a certain distance. This underscores the necessity to incorporate the soil's nonlinear behavior into analyses to ensure precise results.

4.2 Influence of the applied load (F)

The parametric study's initial focus is on the influence of integrating the Pasternak model in its linear and nonlinear formulations. The model incorporates the shear resistance of the soil beneath the geocell, a key factor in realistically modeling the reinforced system's behavior. The parameters adopted for the Pasternak model are as follows: $EI = 7\text{kN.m}^2$, $h_s = 10\text{cm}$, and $G = 5\text{ MPa}$. The applied forces were selected using $F = 1\text{ kN}$, 5 kN , 50 kN , and 100 kN .

Figure 5 compares the displacement profiles along the half-length of the geocell as a function of the parameters mentioned above and the forces applied for the following models.

The results demonstrate that, under all conditions, the maximum displacement is recorded when the point load is applied. A significant reduction in displacement is observed when the Pasternak model is taken into account: a reduction of 54% for the linear model and 75% for the nonlinear model when applying a 100kN force. It is evident that for low values of applied force ($F=1$ and 5kN), the nonlinearity of the Pasternak model does not influence displacement. However, above the dimensionless distance parameter value of 0.8, the influence of the Pasternak model becomes less significant, with a 14% difference observed between the nonlinear Pasternak and Winkler models when a force of 100kN is applied.

Figure 5 Influence of the point load and Pasternak model on geocell displacements: (a) $F = 1$ kN, (b) $F = 5$ kN, (c) $F = 50$ kN, (d) $F = 100$ kN

4.3 Influence of shear modulus G and granular layer thickness h_s

As illustrated in **Figure 6-a**, **6-b**, and **6-c**, the displacements obtained for different values of the shear modulus of the granular layer under the geocell vary depending on the model. The displacement is significantly influenced by the shear strength of the soil beneath the geocell. A reduction of 23% is observed for a shear modulus value of 1MPa between the Winkler model and the nonlinear Pasternak model, and this reduction increases with the shear modulus values; a value of 5MPa gives a reduction of 51%.

In **Figure 6-a**, the displacement profiles of the Pasternak models tend to overlap at lower shear modulus values, indicating that nonlinearity has minimal impact in these conditions.

Figure 6 Influence of shear modulus of granular layer: (a) $G = 1\text{MPa}$, (b) $G = 2\text{MPa}$, (c) $G = 5\text{MPa}$

The results presented in **Figure 7** highlight the influence of the thickness of the granular fill beneath the geocell layer. They were obtained for a relatively low shear modulus of 1MPa and for shear layer thickness $h_s = 50, 100, 200$ and 500mm.

In general, incorporating the shear strength of the soil or introducing a granular shear layer significantly reduces displacements under applied loads on the geocell.

It was observed that increasing the thickness of the granular shear layer amplifies the differences in settlement values obtained using the Winkler model versus the Pasternak model. For a shear layer with a thickness of 50 mm, the difference in maximum displacements between the Winkler model and the nonlinear Pasternak model was 18%. This difference increased to 40.5% for a shear layer with a thickness of 500 mm.

However, the thickness of the shear layer does not significantly influence the displacement values obtained from the linear and nonlinear formulations of the Pasternak model. The differences observed were 10.9% for $h_s = 50$ mm and 7.7% for $h_s = 500$ mm, indicating that the shear behavior of the layer plays a more critical role than its thickness in these formulations.

Figure 7 Effect of Granular Layer Thickness on Geocell Displacement: (a) $h_s = 50\text{mm}$, (b) $h_s = 100\text{mm}$, (c) $h_s = 200\text{mm}$, (d) $h_s = 500\text{mm}$,

According to **Figure 8**, increasing the thickness of the granular layer h_s to 50 cm results in a 27% reduction in displacement in the middle of the geocell layer compared to a thickness of 5 cm. This reduction remains relatively limited compared with the improvements obtained by increasing the shear modulus and, consequently, the shear strength of the granular layer beneath the geocell.

Figure 8 Displacement for different values of hs using the nonlinear Pasternak model

4.4 Influence of the flexural rigidity of the geocell EI

The geocell's flexural rigidity, which is considered a beam in this study, plays an important role in its response. For this analysis, the parametric study focused on the impact of different flexural rigidity (EI) values on the vertical displacements.

Figure 9 Effect of flexural rigidity on Geocell Displacement

As demonstrated in **Figure 9**, an increase in the flexural rigidity EI leads to a modest decrease in maximum displacements, particularly under concentrated loads. This reduction is estimated at 16% for a flexural rigidity range varying from 0.7 kN.m² to 14 kN.m². Additionally, it has been observed that, for values above 2.8 kN.m², the impact of geocell stiffness on displacement becomes negligible. This can be attributed to the integration of the shear strength of the granular layer in the Pasternak model, which plays an important role in limiting the displacements of the geocell, thus surpassing the influence of its flexural rigidity.

5 Conclusion

This study proposed an analytical model to analyze the response of a geocell layer laid on a foundation soil using the nonlinear Winkler and Pasternak models. The geocell is modeled by a beam, with its flexural rigidity taken into account in the calculations, and the underlying soil is represented by nonlinear springs (Winkler model) and a nonlinear shear layer (Pasternak model).

After validating the model, the effect of nonlinearity was investigated by first comparing the linear and nonlinear Winkler models. A significant discrepancy was found in the calculated displacements under concentrated loads applied in the middle of the beam. The nonlinearity leads to an increase in displacements near the load zone, attributable to the high stresses developed in the soil. This deviation decreases as one moves away from the load.

The integration of the Pasternak model, particularly in its nonlinear formulation, considerably reduces geocell displacements by up to 75% for a 100 kN load. However, for low applied forces, the impact of the Pasternak model's nonlinearity remains negligible, underlining the importance of taking into account the soil's shear strength in these cases.

Increasing the shear modulus considerably reduces geocell displacements. A 51% reduction was observed when the shear modulus value increased from 1 to 5 MPa. However, for low values, the displacements calculated by the linear and nonlinear Pasternak models tend to overlap, indicating a small contribution from nonlinearity.

An increase in the thickness of the shear layer reduces the displacement at the center of the geocell layer, but this improvement remains limited compared with the gains obtained by increasing the shear modulus.

Although the flexural rigidity of the soil-geocell composite material is a significant parameter in this type of study, it provides a modest reduction in maximum displacements. Above a certain value, its effect becomes negligible. These results demonstrate that the shear strength of the granular layer beneath the geocell mat governs the response of the reinforced system.

It is essential to recognize certain limitations of this study. The model assumes that the foundation soil and the geocell composite material are homogeneous and exhibit uniform behavior in all directions. However, this does not fully account for the complexity of real conditions, where soil properties can vary. Additionally, boundary effects could lead to discrepancies between the model's predictions and actual behavior. The nonlinear parameters used in the model are derived from simplified assumptions, which may restrict its applicability to various soil types. Future research could benefit from refining the model by incorporating more realistic soil behavior, testing it under a broader range of conditions, and examining how geocell layers interact with multilayered soil foundations.

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